

Annex to: EFSA AHAW Panel (EFSA Panel on Animal Health and Welfare), Nielsen, S. S., Alvarez, J., Boklund, A., Dippel, S., Figuerola, J., Herskin, M. S., Michel, V., Miranda Chueca, M. A., Nannoni, E., Nonno, R., Riber, A. B., Ståhl, K., Stegeman, J. A., Thulke, H.-H., Tuytens, F., Winckler, C., Christiansen, D. H., Olesen, N. J., Rimstad, E., Toffan, A., Vendramin, N., Papaleo, S., Preite, L., Baldinelli, F., Dórea, F. (2025). Viral haemorrhagic septicaemia virus, infectious haematopoietic necrosis virus and HPR-deleted infectious salmon anaemia virus – Risk of introduction in free areas through fertilised eggs and gametes. *EFSA Journal*, 23(12), e9800. <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2025.9800>

© European Food Safety Authority, 2025

Annex B Expert knowledge elicitation

This Annex presents the detailed results of the expert elicitation conducted by the five experts of EFSA's working group set up to address this mandate. Results are presented by scenario and virus. Please note that probabilities related to VHSV and IHNV have been estimated together. For a full description of scenarios please see Section 3.3.1 in the scientific opinion. Tables B.1 and B.2 report the overall reasoning provided by all the experts for the final probability of effectiveness of each risk mitigation measure assessed (as reported in Section 3.3.3 in the scientific opinion) related to scenarios 1 and 2, respectively. Figures B.1–B.27 report the expert's individual estimate for each probability. The probability terms and values the experts used in this elicitation are in table B.3.

TABLE B.1 Final range and reasoning for the probability of failure for the risk mitigation measures considered in Scenario 1 (elicited by the five EFSA experts).

Question asked	Virus	Final range for the probability of failure (min. – max.)	Reasoning provided
RMM1: individual testing	VHSV or IHNV	1–10%	According to published validation of the real time PCR recommended by EURLFISH, values are indicated and are in general: sensitivity >95%, and specificity >98 %. One expert pointed out that fish are immune suppressed at sexual maturation, implying that the virus is usually high in load. Another responded, however, that since the virus has not been detected, it should be assumed that the positive fish is subclinically infected with relatively low amounts of VHSV/IHNV. Considering this potential low viral load, and technical issues related to RNA extraction, false negatives cannot be excluded. The overall probability of false negatives was considered low due to the high sensitivity of the recommended real-time qPCR method applied to target organs, which provides the most optimal possibility of detecting an infected animal.
	HPR-deleted ISAV	1–15%	The same reasoning as provided for VHSV or IHNV was discussed, once again stressing that this assumes use of the recommended RTqPCR. Probability of failure was considered to have a slightly higher upper bound because less precise information is available about test sensitivity, and because subclinical cases can persist much longer than for VHS and IHN.
	VHSV or IHNV	1–20%	Overall, experts were in agreement that 'Disinfection during water hardening is very efficient if conducted

RMM2a: Disinfection of eggs, green			correctly', stressing several times the importance of being correctly applied. One expert was of the opinion that the protocol suggested by WOAH is quite 'mild', stressing that 10 minutes is the <i>minimum</i> time for disinfection. The overall probability of failure was considered due to potential improper application of the method, kept at no more than 20% due to the overwhelming positive experience of experts with successful disinfection in the field.
	HPR-deleted ISAV	1–10%	Same comments as provided above for VHSV and IHNV. In addition, one expert explicitly mentioned: 'Our screenings in the laboratory have demonstrated that the relative load of ISAV in the ovarian fluids is significantly lower than in organs. Thus if the fish are subclinically infected with low viral load, RT-qPCR screenings in our laboratory have demonstrated that the ovarian fluids are negative. However, although proper disinfection is applied to the green eggs and the equipment used for stripping, there is always a risk of human or technical error'.
RMM2b: Disinfection of eggs, eyed	VHSV or IHNV	1–20%	Same overall reasoning as for disinfection applied to green eggs. Once again the probability of failure was largely considered attributable to technical errors in application of the method, including not properly rinsing the eggs with pathogen free water. The need for proper biosecurity measures and proper application of the disinfection protocol was stressed several times.
	HPR-deleted ISAV	1–7%	Same reasoning and comments as above, with an even lower range of failure because the potential virus load in hardened (eyed) eggs is expected to be even lower than in green eggs.
RMM3: Disinfection of eggs, on arrival	VHSV or IHNV	1–10%	The same overall comments about disinfection at other stages were given, stressing here that once the eggs arrive at the farm, this last disinfection should only kill viruses potentially cross contaminating the egg batch.
	HPR-deleted ISAV	1–9%	Same overall comments as for all disinfection steps above.

TABLE B.2 Final range and reasoning for the probability of failure for the risk mitigation measures considered in Scenario 2 (elicited by the five EFSA experts).

Question asked	Virus	Final range for the probability of FAILURE (min. – max.)	Reasoning provided
RMM1: individual testing	VHSV or IHNV	5–33%	This scenario was interpreted to reflect medium- to small-scale production, reflecting the main types of European production of rainbow trout, which are highly susceptible to VHSV/IHNV. Overall there is high level of trust in the sensitivity of the test, with greater range of probability of failure compared with individual testing just because of the added uncertainty about whether positive animals would be included in the sample tested. It was stressed, however, that trout, the main species to which this scenario would apply, are highly susceptible to the virus, and if high mortality is always investigated, and the establishment can be trusted to monitor the health status of the population, the likelihood of undetected viral circulation is very low.

			In this scenario, experts were also asked to evaluate the effectiveness of applying an extra test to the broodstock as an epidemiological group (as opposed to the testing applied to the whole establishment to ensure the health status of the population). The same reasons for uncertainty were found, largely related to whether positive animals would be sampled, and the resulting estimated probability range was found to be 5-25% .
	HPR-deleted ISAV	5-33%	The same overall comments as above were discussed. It is important to stress that this scenario was evaluated because the experts' felt that it was needed to reflect production practices in Europe for rainbow trout. This species, however, has very low susceptibility to ISAV (the infection of HPR-deleted ISAV in rainbow trout was deemed almost impossible by experts).
RMM2a: Disinfection of eggs, green	VHSV or IHN	1-20%	All the same as for Scenario 1.
	HPR-deleted ISAV	1-10%	
RMM2b: Disinfection of eggs, eyed	VHSV or IHN	1-20%	
	HPR-deleted ISAV	1-7%	
RMM3: Disinfection of eggs, on arrival	VHSV or IHN	1-10%	
	HPR-deleted ISAV	1-9%	

TABLE B.3 Probability ranges provided as references during expert elicitation.

Subject probability range (%)	Probability term
0-1	Almost impossible
1-5	Extremely unlikely
5-10	Very unlikely
10-33	Unlikely
33-66	About as likely as not
66-90	Likely
90-95	Very likely
95-99	Extremely likely
99-100	Almost certain

Scenario 1-VHSV/IHNV

RMM1: Assuming that this individual is infected with the virus, what is the probability that the individual will NOT be detected as positive (test is false negative)?

FIGURE B.1 Individual probability ranges, after the collective judgement, estimating the probability that the individual infected with VHSV/IHNV will not be detected as positive (Scenario 1). The pink continuous line at the bottom indicates the final range.

Scenario 1-VHSV/IHNV

RMM2a: What is the probability that contaminated GREEN fertilized eggs would remain infected (virus still present) after properly applying the disinfection protocol as documented?

FIGURE B.2 Individual probability ranges, after the collective judgement, estimating the probability that contaminated green fertilised eggs would remain infected with VHSV/IHNV after properly applying the disinfection protocol (Scenario 1). The pink continuous line at the bottom indicates the final range.

Scenario 1-VHSV/IHNV

RMM2b: What is the probability that contaminated EYED fertilized eggs would remain infected (virus still present) after properly applying the disinfection protocol as documented? (Assume they were NOT disinfected before, or that failed)

FIGURE B.3 Individual probability ranges, after the collective judgement, estimating the probability that contaminated eyed fertilised eggs would remain infected with VHSV/IHNV after properly applying the disinfection protocol (Scenario 1). The pink continuous line at the bottom indicates the final range.

Scenario 1-VHSV/IHNV

RMM3: What is the probability that contaminated fertilized eggs would remain infected (virus still present) after properly applying the disinfection protocol as documented?

FIGURE B.4 Individual probability ranges, after the collective judgement, estimating the probability that contaminated fertilised eggs would remain infected with VHSV/IHNV after properly applying the disinfection protocol (Scenario 1). The pink continuous line at the bottom indicates the final range.

Scenario 1-ISAV HPR-deleted

RMM1: Assuming that this individual is infected with the virus, what is the probability that the individual will NOT be detected as positive (test is false negative)?

FIGURE B.5 Individual probability ranges, after the collective judgement, estimating the probability that the individual infected with HPR-deleted ISAV will not be detected as positive (Scenario 1). The pink continuous line at the bottom indicates the final range.

Scenario 1-ISAV HPR-deleted

RMM2a: What is the probability that contaminated GREEN fertilized eggs would remain infected (virus still present) after properly applying the disinfection protocol as documented?

FIGURE B.6 Individual probability ranges, after the collective judgement, estimating the probability that contaminated green fertilised eggs would remain infected with HPR-deleted ISAV after properly applying the disinfection protocol (Scenario 1). The pink continuous line at the bottom indicates the final range.

Scenario 1-ISAV HPR-deleted

RMM2b: What is the probability that contaminated EYED fertilized eggs would remain infected (virus still present) after properly applying the disinfection protocol as documented? (Assume they were NOT disinfected before, or that failed)

FIGURE B.7 Individual probability ranges, after the collective judgement, estimating the probability that contaminated eyed fertilised eggs would remain infected with HPR-deleted ISAV after properly applying the disinfection protocol (Scenario 1). The pink continuous line at the bottom indicates the final range.

Scenario 1-ISAV HPR-deleted

RMM3: What is the probability that contaminated fertilized eggs would remain infected (virus still present) after properly applying the disinfection protocol as documented?

FIGURE B.8 Individual probability ranges, after the collective judgement, estimating the probability that contaminated fertilised eggs would remain infected with HPR-deleted ISAV after properly applying the disinfection protocol (Scenario 1). The pink continuous line at the bottom indicates the final range.

Scenario 1-ISAV HPR0

RMM1: Assuming that this individual is infected with the virus, what is the probability that the individual will NOT be detected as positive (test is false negative)?

FIGURE B.9 Individual probability ranges, after the collective judgement, estimating the probability that the individual infected with ISAV HPR0 will not be detected as positive (Scenario 1). The pink continuous line at the bottom indicates the final range.

Scenario 1-ISAV HPR0

RMM2a: What is the probability that contaminated GREEN fertilized eggs would remain infected (virus still present) after properly applying the disinfection protocol as documented?

FIGURE B.10 Individual probability ranges, after the collective judgement, estimating the probability that contaminated green fertilised eggs would remain infected with ISAV HPR0 after properly applying the disinfection protocol (Scenario 1). The pink continuous line at the bottom indicates the final range.

Scenario 1-ISAV HPR0

RMM2b: What is the probability that contaminated EYED fertilized eggs would remain infected (virus still present) after properly applying the disinfection protocol as documented? (Assume they were NOT disinfected before, or that failed)

FIGURE B.11 Individual probability ranges, after the collective judgement, estimating the probability that contaminated eyed fertilised eggs would remain infected with ISAV HPR0 after properly applying the disinfection protocol (Scenario 1). The pink continuous line at the bottom indicates the final range.

Scenario 1-ISAV HPR0

RMM3: What is the probability that contaminated fertilized eggs would remain infected (virus still present) after properly applying the disinfection protocol as documented?

FIGURE B.12 Individual probability ranges, after the collective judgement, estimating the probability that contaminated fertilised eggs would remain infected with ISAV HPR0 after properly applying the disinfection protocol (Scenario 1). The pink continuous line at the bottom indicates the final range.

Scenario 2-VHSV/IHNV

RMM1: What is the probability that the virus is present in the population but has not been detected, if the health status of the establishment is checked using population testing following EU regulation (i.e. testing 75 fish)?

FIGURE B.13 Individual probability ranges, after the collective judgement, estimating the probability that VHSV/IHNV is present in the population, but has not been detected, if the health status is checked using population testing following EU regulation (Scenario 2). The pink continuous line at the bottom indicates the final range.

Scenario 2-VHSV/IHNV

RMM2a: What is the probability that contaminated GREEN fertilized eggs would remain infected (virus still present) after properly applying the disinfection protocol as documented?

FIGURE B.14 Individual probability ranges, after the collective judgement, estimating the probability that contaminated green fertilised eggs would remain infected with VHSV/IHNV after properly applying the disinfection protocol (Scenario 2). The pink continuous line at the bottom indicates the final range.

Scenario 2-VHSV/IHNV

RMM2b: What is the probability that contaminated EYED fertilized eggs would remain infected (virus still present) after properly applying the disinfection protocol as documented? (Assume they were NOT disinfected before, or that failed)

FIGURE B.15 Individual probability ranges, after the collective judgement, estimating the probability that contaminated eyed fertilised eggs would remain infected with VHSV/IHNV after properly applying the disinfection protocol (Scenario 2). The pink continuous line at the bottom indicates the final range.

Scenario 2-VHSV/IHNV

RMM3: What is the probability that contaminated fertilized eggs would remain infected (virus still present) after properly applying the disinfection protocol as documented?

FIGURE B.16 Individual probability ranges, after the collective judgement, estimating the probability that contaminated fertilised eggs would remain infected with VHSV/IHNV after properly applying the disinfection protocol (Scenario 2). The pink continuous line at the bottom indicates the final range.

Scenario 2-VHSV/IHNV

RMM4: Assuming that at least one individual is infected with the virus among the broodstock, what is the probability that the test applied to 30 animals as 3 pool up to 10 will FAIL to detect the virus (sample fails to include a positive animal or test is false negative)?

FIGURE B.17 Individual probability ranges, after the collective judgement, estimating the probability that VHSV or IHNV remains undetected when testing 30 broodstock animals using a pooled testing strategy (pools of up to 10 animals each) (Scenario 2). The pink continuous line at the bottom indicates the final range.

Scenario 2-ISAV HPR-deleted

RMM1: What is the probability that the virus is present in the population but has not been detected, if the health status of the establishment is checked using population testing following EU regulation (i.e. testing 75 fish)?

FIGURE B.18 Individual probability ranges, after the collective judgement, estimating the probability that HPR-deleted ISAV is present in the population, but has not been detected, if the health status is checked using population testing following EU regulation (Scenario 2). The pink continuous line at the bottom indicates the final range.

Scenario 2-ISAV HPR-deleted

RMM2a: What is the probability that contaminated GREEN fertilized eggs would remain infected (virus still present) after properly applying the disinfection protocol as documented?

FIGURE B.19 Individual probability ranges, after the collective judgement, estimating the probability that contaminated green fertilised eggs would remain infected with HPR-deleted ISAV after properly applying the disinfection protocol (Scenario 2). The pink continuous line at the bottom indicates the final range.

Scenario 2-ISAV HPR-deleted

RMM2b: What is the probability that contaminated EYED fertilized eggs would remain infected (virus still present) after properly applying the disinfection protocol as documented? (Assume they were NOT disinfected before, or that failed)

FIGURE B.20 Individual probability ranges, after the collective judgement, estimating the probability that contaminated eyed fertilised eggs would remain infected with HPR-deleted ISAV after properly applying the disinfection protocol (Scenario 2). The pink continuous line at the bottom indicates the final range.

Scenario 2-ISAV HPR-deleted

RMM3: What is the probability that contaminated fertilized eggs would remain infected (virus still present) after properly applying the disinfection protocol as documented?

FIGURE B.21 Individual probability ranges, after the collective judgement, estimating the probability that contaminated fertilised eggs would remain infected with HPR-deleted ISAV after properly applying the disinfection protocol (Scenario 2). The pink continuous line at the bottom indicates the final range.

Scenario 2-ISAV HPR-deleted

RMM4: Assuming that at least one individual is infected with the virus among the broodstock, what is the probability that the test applied to 30 animals pooled up to 5 will FAIL to detect the virus (sample fails to include a positive animal or test is false negative)?

FIGURE B.22 Individual probability ranges, after the collective judgement, estimating the probability that HPR-deleted ISAV remains undetected when testing 30 broodstock animals using a pooled testing strategy (pools of up to 5 animals each) (Scenario 2). The pink continuous line at the bottom indicates the final range.

Scenario 2-ISAV HPR0

RMM1: What is the probability that the virus is present in the population but has not been detected, if the health status of the establishment is checked using population testing following EU regulation (i.e. testing 75 fish)?

FIGURE B.23 Individual probability ranges, after the collective judgement, estimating the probability that ISAV HPR0 is present in the population, but has not been detected, if the health status is checked using population testing following EU regulation (i.e. sampling and testing internal organs is applied). The pink continuous line at the bottom indicates the final range.

Scenario 2-ISAV HPR0

RMM2a: What is the probability that contaminated GREEN fertilized eggs would remain infected (virus still present) after properly applying the disinfection protocol as documented?

FIGURE B.24 Individual probability ranges, after the collective judgement, estimating the probability that contaminated green fertilised eggs would remain infected with ISAV HPR0 after properly applying the disinfection protocol (Scenario 2). The pink continuous line at the bottom indicates the final range.

Scenario 2-ISAV HPR0

RMM2b: What is the probability that contaminated EYED fertilized eggs would remain infected (virus still present) after properly applying the disinfection protocol as documented? (Assume they were NOT disinfected before, or that failed)

FIGURE B.25 Individual probability ranges, after the collective judgement, estimating the probability that contaminated eyed fertilised eggs would remain infected with ISAV HPR0 after properly applying the disinfection protocol (Scenario 2). The pink continuous line at the bottom indicates the final range.

Scenario 2-ISAV HPR0

RMM3: What is the probability that contaminated fertilized eggs would remain infected (virus still present) after properly applying the disinfection protocol as documented?

FIGURE B.26 Individual probability ranges, after the collective judgement, estimating the probability that contaminated fertilised eggs would remain infected with ISAV HPR0 after properly applying the disinfection protocol (Scenario 2). The pink continuous line at the bottom indicates the final range.

Scenario 2-ISAV HPR0

RMM4: Assuming that at least one individual is infected with the virus among the broodstock, what is the probability that the test applied to 30 animals pooled up to 5 will FAIL to detect the virus (sample fails to include a positive animal or test is false negative)?

FIGURE B.27: Individual probability ranges, after the collective judgement, estimating the probability that ISAV HPR0 remains undetected when testing 30 broodstock animals using a pooled testing strategy (3 pools of up to 5 animals each) (Scenario 2) sampling internal organs. The pink continuous line at the bottom indicates the final range.